

strong aya

A new, interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder European network to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for Adolescents and Young Adults with cancer.

The future of cancer therapy

Deliverable Report

WP1: Midterm recruitment report study 1

Deliverable D1.11

Due date of deliverable: 30.06.23

Actual submission date: 28/06/2023

Project:	STRONG-AYA
Lead Contributor	Anne-Sophie Darlington, Nicole Collaço, Kirsty Way
Email	A.Darlington@soton.ac.uk
Other Contributors	
Emails	

Due date	30.06.23
Delivery date	28.06.23
Deliverable type	R
Dissemination level	PU

Description of Work	Version	Date
	V1.0	28/06/2023

Description:

This report includes an overview of the number of recruited participants, problems in recruitment and, implemented and planned measures to mitigate potential delays in WP1 (qualitative and Delphi study).

Summary

The aim of Work Package 1 (WP1) of STRONG AYA is to develop a Core Outcome Set for adolescents and young adults (AYAs) with cancer. This will be done through three phases; 1) a review of the literature to identify relevant outcomes for AYAs with cancer, 2) qualitative interviews with AYAs with /who have had a diagnosis of cancer, parents/partners/siblings of AYAs and healthcare professionals/other professionals who provide care to AYAs, to generate a complete list of outcomes of relevance to AYAs with cancer, and 3) conducting a Delphi study. We report on the recruitment of participants for the qualitative and Delphi study.

1 Table of Contents

SUMMARY	3
1 TABLE OF CONTENTS	4
2 DEFINITIONS	5
3 ABBREVIATIONS	6
4 INTRODUCTION	7
4.1 PROJECT BACKGROUND	7
4.2 DELIVERABLE INTRODUCTION	9
5 RECRUITMENT	9
6 CONCLUSION	14

2 Definitions

STRONG AYA consortium members are referred to as following within this text:

1. **NKI-AVL** – Stichting het Nederlands Kanker Instituut – Antoni van Leeuwenhoek Ziekenhuis (NL)
2. **YCE** – Youth Cancer Europe (RO)
3. **INT** – Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Nazionale dei Tumori (IT)
4. **FFUND** – FFUND BV (NL)
5. **CLB** – Centre de Lutte Contre le Cancer Leon Berard (FR)
6. **ECO** – European Cancer Organisation (BE)
7. **UNIMAAS** – Universiteit Maastricht (NL)
8. **IKNL** – Stichting Integraal Kankercentrum Nederland (NL)
9. **EORTC** – European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer AISBL (BE)
10. **IGR** – Institut Gustave Roussy (FR)
11. **MSCNRIO** – Narodowy Instytut Onkologii im. Marii Skłodowskiej-Curie – Państwowy Instytut Badawczy (Marie Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology) (PL)
12. **UOM** – University of Manchester (UK)
13. **UOL** – University of Leeds (UK)
14. **LTHT** – Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust (UL)
15. **SOUTHAMPTON** – University of Southampton (UK)

- **Grant Agreement** (including its annexes and amendments): the agreement signed between the beneficiaries of the HORIZON Research and Innovations Actions (hereafter referred to as Horizon) and the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (hereafter referred to as HADEA) for the undertaking of the STRONG AYA project (Grant Agreement no. 101057482).
- **Beneficiary**: Signatories of the Grant Agreement
- **Associated Partner**: Entities which participate in the action but without the right to charge costs or claim contributions.
- **Project**: the sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
- **Consortium**: the STRONG AYA consortium, including all the aforementioned partners.
- **Consortium Agreement**: The agreement made between STRONG AYA members for the implementation and execution of the action outlined in the Grant Agreement. The agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to HADEA on behalf of the European Union, and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

3 Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning
HCP	Healthcare Professional
PRO	Patient Reported Outcome
PROM	Patient Reported Outcome Measure
COS	Core Outcome Set
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Lead(s)
WP1	Work Package 1 (Development Core Outcome Set AYA with cancer & data collection)
WP2	Work Package 2 (Governance, Data Security and Ethics)
WP3	Work Package 3 (Infrastructure and Interoperability)
WP4	Work Package 4 (Operation of STRONG AYA ecosystems, stakeholder and patient involvement, dissemination, exploitation, communication)
WP5	Work Package 5 (Scientific coordination and project management)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OA	Open Access
PAB	Patient Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
SC	Steering Committee
MT	Management Team

4 Introduction

4.1 Project background

Cancer at adolescent and young adult (AYA) age is rare, although 4-6 times more frequent than paediatric cancer (i.e. prepubescent period). However, this rarity does not reflect the significant personal and societal costs of cancer in this population, as reflected in the potential years of life lost or saved, the decreased productivity and quality-of-life due to the impact of the disease during formative years, and the long-term complications or disabilities¹. AYAs with cancer form a unique group; they face age-specific issues (e.g. Infertility, unemployment, financial problems) and decreased quality of life due to cancer and its treatment. Unlike dedicated healthcare and trials for paediatric cancer patients, AYA-specific healthcare services are scarce and vary across Europe. AYAs who are at the core of society and economy need access to age-appropriate and high-quality healthcare.

Defining AYAs with cancer as 15 to 39 years at initial cancer diagnosis², their annual cancer incidence is 42.2/100.000, with 156.431 cases in Europe and 1.231.007 cases worldwide reported in 2018 (together 6.8% of all cancers)³. Population-based data from 27 European countries supports that AYAs have lower survival than children but higher than adults affected by cancer. Advances in cancer treatment have led to increased survival rates for AYAs with cancer, improving by 82% for all cancers between 1990 and 2007⁴.

However, survival improvement in AYA is more challenging than for children and older cancer survivors, which might be due to the fact that AYA have the highest absolute excess risk of second primary malignant neoplasms⁵. AYA face some distinct challenges given that they do not belong to neither paediatric nor adult oncology groups. Characteristic features of this population group include unique spectrum of cancer types, different tumour biology, unique complex psychological needs, distinct late sequelae, including impaired fertility, and palliative care. These traits imply that clinical management, treatment, diagnosis, psychological support will need to be designed and developed for AYA's specific needs. For example, AYAs diagnosed with breast and prostate carcinomas have worse survival than older patients because of the biological differences between them, highlighting the need to target screening methodologies, treatment and policies to their needs⁶. AYAs with cancer also face significant psychological challenges, including substance abuse, mental health issues, suicidal ideations and increased emotional burden from cancer and cancer-related morbidity. Finally, tailoring cancer care to AYA's needs is difficult and due to many different complex factors including the low rate of participation by AYAs in clinical trials and cancer research⁷.

Despite the increasing awareness and a growing body of the scientific literature, these unique issues remain to be fully recognised and addressed by the European health systems and AYAs with cancer are frequently underserved. In part, this may have resulted from the traditional dichotomy between the

¹ Stoneham SJ. AYA survivorship: The next challenge. *Cancer* 2020; 126: 2116-2119.

² Adolescent and Young Adult Oncology Review Group. Closing the gap: Research and Care Imperatives for Adolescents and Young Adults with Cancer. National Institute of Health, National Cancer Institute, and Livestrong Young Adult Alliance: Bethesda, MD, USA, 2006.

³ Trama A, Botta L, Steliarova-Foucher E. Cancer Burden in Adolescents and Young Adults: A Review of Epidemiological Evidence. *Cancer J* 2018; 24: 256-266

⁴ Trama A, Botta L, Foschi R et al. Survival of European adolescents and young adults diagnosed with cancer in 2000-07: population-based data from EURO-CARE-5. *Lancet Oncol* 2016; 17: 896-906.

⁵ Keegan THM, Bleyer A, Rosenberg AS et al. Second Primary Malignant Neoplasms and Survival in Adolescent and Young Adult Cancer Survivors. *JAMA Oncol* 2017; 3: 1554-1557.

⁶ Stark D, Bielack S, Brugieres L et al. Teenagers and young adults with cancer in Europe: from national programmes to a European integrated coordinated project. *European Journal of Cancer Care*, 25(3), 419-427.

⁷ Hayashi RJ. Adolescent and young adult cancer survivorship: The new frontier for investigation. *Cancer* 2019; 125: 1976-1978.

integrated paediatric (“patient/family-centred”) care services versus dispersed (“disease-centered”) adult oncology services^{8,9,10}. Up to half of AYAs with cancer report unmet informational and service needs, impacting their direct (survival rates) and indirect (long term effects and mental health) recovery to participate in society¹¹.

Furthermore, aligned with this barrier is the low rate of health care utilisation by AYAs, especially primary care, given their challenges to sustain health insurance coverage¹². According to a survey conducted through the networks of the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOP Europe), 67% of practitioners do not have access to specialised centres for AYA with cancer, 67% had no access to a specialist cancer service for late effects management and 38% had no access to fertility specialists. Under-provision and inequality of AYA cancer care is common across Europe and especially in the Eastern and Southern-East. Furthermore, the Working Group also reported an absence of outcome measures for monitoring and evaluating AYA cancer care programs and control¹³.

Among the recommended future steps, it has been identified that one of the most important contributions to AYA research would be to pool data (e.g. patient-reported outcomes, clinical and treatment data) across institutions and countries and create large cohorts for researchers to address the burden of cancer in AYA¹⁴. There is a lack of data standardization, data interoperability and (prospective) collection of outcomes of relevance for AYAs with cancer.

The STRONG-AYA project aims to tackle the underrepresentation of AYA’s experiences and outcomes when navigating the healthcare system and in clinical care by developing national infrastructures for outcome data management and clinical decision-making within a pan-European ecosystem and establishing communication feedback for AYAs with cancer and the healthcare systems. This will be key to improving healthcare services, research, outcomes and policies for AYAs and to ultimately better cancer care for this patient group.

To this aim, STRONG AYA brings together an international multi-disciplinary consortium across seven European countries, led by the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI) and composed of academic research organisations (European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC), University of Southampton, University of Leeds, University of Manchester, Maastricht University, Netherlands Comprehensive Cancer Organisation (IKNL)), clinical partners (Italian National Tumour Institute, Léon Bérard Centre, Gustave Roussy Institute, Maria Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology, the Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust), stakeholder and patient organisations (Youth Cancer Europe, European Cancer Organisation) and a consulting company (FFUND).

Building on previous initiatives, a STRONG-AYA data ecosystem will be set up for value-based care, research and policy for AYA with cancer by:

⁸ Ferrari A, Stark D, Peccatori FA et al. Adolescents and young adults (AYA) with cancer: a position paper from the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOPe). *ESMO Open* 2021; 6: 100096.

⁹ Osborn M, Johnson R, Thompson K et al. Models of care for adolescent and young adult cancer programs. *Pediatr Blood Cancer* 2019; 66: e27991.

¹⁰ Fardell JE, Patterson P, Wakefield CE et al. A Narrative Review of Models of Care for Adolescents and Young Adults with Cancer: Barriers and Recommendations. *J Adolesc Young Adult Oncol* 2018; 7: 148-152.

¹¹ Keegan TH, Lichtensztajn DY, Kato I et al. Unmet adolescent and young adult cancer survivors information and service needs: a population-based cancer registry study. *J Cancer Surviv* 2012; 6: 239-250.

¹² Hayashi RJ. Adolescent and young adult cancer survivorship: The new frontier for investigation. *Cancer* 2019; 125: 1976-1978.

¹³ Saloustrous E, Stark D, Michailidou K et al. Report on ESMO/SIOPE European Landscape project key results: Mapping the status and needs in AYA cancer care. *Late-breaking and deferred publication abstracts public health* 2017; 28, 5: V643.

¹⁴ Smith AW, Seibel NL, Lewis DR et al. Next steps for adolescent and young adult oncology workshop: An update on progress and recommendations for the future. *Cancer* 2016; 122: 988-999.

1. **Developing a Core Outcome Set (COS)** specifically for AYAs with cancer, via a participative consensus process defining most important aspects for those directly affected by AYA cancer, including patients and healthcare professionals (WP1).
2. **Implementing the COS across several national European healthcare systems.** Data will be collected at local level and will then be included in a data integration platform. An overall ecosystem framework for data analytics and output will be created supporting federated analyses and the creation of reports across clinical and patient-reported data and making national repositories of (patient-reported) health data, available to individual patients, patient organisations, regulatory authorities, as well as the patients' health care providers to inform clinical decision-making. The five resulting **national ecosystems** will be connected to each other into **the pan-European ecosystem** using a federated approach also utilizing the overall ecosystem framework.
3. **Disseminating the COS to a wide range of local as well as pan-European stakeholders,** in particular by developing analytical tools to process and present patient outcome data and establish feedback loops that inform patients and clinicians.

STRONG AYA will enable AYA care and research to benefit from collection and pooling of patient-centered data and collaboration among all stakeholders: patients, healthcare professionals, scientists, and policymakers. More widely, the project will leverage the network of interested organisations and networks established under STRONG AYA for long-term strengthened promotion of the necessary implementation of specialist AYA cancer services across Europe. This will ultimately bring novel insights into AYA cancer care, research and policy, contributing to the long-term improvement of outcomes for people with AYA cancer.

4.2 Deliverable introduction

WP1 (developing a core outcome set): The overall aim of WP1 is to develop a Core Outcome Set for AYAs with cancer. We aim to assess which outcomes including patient-reported outcomes, clinical, and treatment data, are most important to assess for AYAs with cancer, from the point of view of AYAs with cancer, healthcare professionals and other stakeholders, to arrive at a consensus. This will be done through three phases; 1) a review of the literature to identify relevant outcomes for AYAs with cancer, 2) qualitative interviews with AYAs with cancer/who have had a diagnosis of cancer, parents/partners/siblings and healthcare professionals who provide care to AYAs to generate a complete list of outcomes of relevance to AYAs with cancer, and 3) conducting a Delphi study. The Delphi technique is used for achieving convergence of opinion from all stakeholders (with equal contributions) on the importance of different outcomes in multiple anonymised prioritisation rounds. A three-round survey will be sent to stakeholders asking questions around outcomes relevant to AYAs cancer care ranking them based on perceived level of importance.

This report shall include an overview of the number of recruited participants for the interviews and Delphi study, problems in recruitment and, planned measures to mitigate any potential incurred delays.

5 Recruitment

Recruitment

The study was approved by the Southampton University Ethics committee, reference: ERGO 78653 (15/03/23).

Three groups of participants were recruited for the qualitative interviews; adolescents and young adults (AYAs) with/who had cancer between the ages of 15-39 years, healthcare/other professionals who provide care for AYAs with cancer, and parents/caregivers/spouses/siblings of AYAs. We intended to recruit up to 30 AYAs with cancer, 25 healthcare professionals/other professionals who provide care to AYAs with cancer and up to 20 parents/caregivers/partners/siblings of AYAs with cancer. Interviews were conducted between April 2023-June 2023.

Participants were recruited in the following ways:

AYAs	Parents/caregivers/ partners/siblings	Healthcare professionals/other professionals
<p>Youth Cancer Europe charity: contact at charity emailed potential participants.</p> <p>Youth Cancer Europe advertised study through social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook).</p>	Asking each AYA interviewed if their parent/partner/sibling would take part in an interview.	(Inter)national AYA oncology networks (via ENTYAC, ESMO-SIOPE)) by email/newsletter.
Twitter post (hosted by research group’s Twitter page at University of Southampton) and retweeted by others.	Contact at Cancer charity centre in UK recruited (gave out PIS for study) eligible participants that go to the centre.	Participants interviewed recommended other professionals to potentially approach for participation.
Social media (Facebook group) of youth cancer group through a lead cancer hospital Trust in the UK.	UK cancer support groups/charities (Ovacome Family/friends support group, CancerWise, Carers Support Wessex Sussex support group, Live Through This peer support group, Haematology Transplant Patient Family Group).	EORTC sent email about study to their members.
Participants interviewed directed other AYAs to take part in an interview.	Dutch cancer carer networks.	

Table 1. Recruitment pathways for interviews

Youth Cancer Europe were deemed the most appropriate pathway to recruit AYAs due to their wide network and good relations with AYAs across Europe. Pragmatically, and from an ethical process view point, this was easier to set up than recruiting via clinicians across different hospitals across Europe. Social media was also viewed to be a good avenue to recruit AYAs, as many AYAs are engaged with various social media platforms.

	AYAs	Parents/caregivers/ partners/siblings	Healthcare professionals/other professionals
Recruited	38	10	30

Completed	27	4	25
Response rate	71.1%	40.0%	83.3%

Table 2. Response rates from interviews

Demographics of participants

AYAs						
Age at interview (range)	Age at diagnosis (range)	Sex	Ethnicity	Nationality	Diagnosis	On/off treatment
(23-43 years)	(15-36 years)	F (n=18) M (n=9)	White (n=17) White/Latino (n=1) Hispanic (n=1) Caucasian (n=8)	British (n=7) Portuguese (n=3) Polish (n=2) Romanian (n=2) Belgian (n=2) Czech (n=1) Croatian (n=1) Dutch (n=1) Greek (n=1) Lithuanian (n=1) Slovenian (n=1) Spanish (n=1) Swedish (n=1) Ukrainian (n=1) Armenian (n=1) Costa Rica/Dutch (n=1)	Leukemia (n=7) Hodgkins Lymphoma (n=8) Non Hodgkins Lymphoma (n=2) Sarcoma (n=3) Ovarian (n=3) Breast (n=1) Appendix (n=1) Pancreatic (n=1) Multiple cancers (n=1)	Off treatment (n=24) On treatment (n=3)

Table 3. Demographics of AYA participants

Parents/caregivers/partners/siblings						
Age at interview (range)	Age at child/partner/siblings diagnosis (range)	Sex	Ethnicity	Nationality	Diagnosis of child/partner/siblings diagnosis	On/off treatment
(26-63 years)	(25-43 years)	F (n=2) M (n=2)	White (n=1) Caucasian (n=2) Latino (n=1)	British (n=1) Swedish (n=1) Dutch/Costa Rican (n=1) Lithuanian (n=1)	Hodgkins Lymphoma (n=3) Leukaemia (n=1)	Off treatment (n=3) On treatment (n=1)

Table 4. Demographics of parents/caregivers/partners/siblings participants

Healthcare/other professionals					
Age	Sex	Nationality	Profession	Experience	Core expertise
(28-65 years)	F (n=17) M (n=8)	British (n=10) Belgian (n=2) Dutch (n=2) Portuguese (n=2) Polish (n=2) Czech (n=1) French (n=1) Italian (n=1) Indian (n=1) Norwegian (n=1) Swedish (n=1) New Zealander/British (n=1)	Oncologist (n=6) Consultant (n=2) Senior consultant (n=1) Surgical oncologist (n=1) Clinical psychologist (n=1) Paediatrician (n=1) Nurse specialist (n=4) Lead nurse (n=3) Nurse practitioner (n=2) AYA co-ordinator (n=1) Medical social worker (n=1) Counsellor (n=1) Researcher (n=1)	6 months-34 years	Teenage and young adult oncology/AYA cancer care (n=9) Oncology (n=4) Haematology oncology (n=2) Paediatric oncology (n=1) Paediatric & adolescents (n=1) Psychology (n=1) Early phase clinical trials (n=1) Early drug development, epidemiology and cancer and preventative oncology (n=1) Leukaemia's (n=1) Gastrointestinal oncology (n=1) AYA sarcomas/brain tumours (n=1) AYA bone and soft tissue sarcoma AYA breast, testicular and neuroendocrine cancer (n=1)

Table 5. Demographics of healthcare/other professional participants

The majority of AYA participants were recruited through Youth Cancer Europe charity, and some through the social media page associated with a cancer treating hospital in the United Kingdom. Parents/caregivers/partners/siblings were recruited through the AYAs that had been interviewed. Healthcare professionals were approached through email via SIOPE and EORTC.

Recruitment challenges of qualitative interviews

Whilst we achieved our recruitment target of interviewing up to 30 AYAs and 25 healthcare professionals, challenges were encountered in the recruitment of the parent/caregiver/partner/sibling stakeholder group. Although various pathways to recruit this stakeholder group were engaged with (see Table 1), the response rate was low. For pragmatic reasons and to not incur delays to the next phase of the work package, we will close recruitment to parents/caregivers/partners/siblings for the qualitative study (as of 28.06.23). Should any participant from this stakeholder group contact the lead researcher to express interest in taking part in a qualitative interview, they will be encouraged to participate in the Delphi study.

Recruitment plan for the Delphi study

The first round of the Delphi study will be emailed to stakeholders in the first week of September, 2023. Subsequent rounds will be emailed to stakeholders 2-3 weeks after the previous round has closed. Each round will be open for 3 weeks to give the stakeholders an opportunity to complete the Delphi survey. An amendment to the protocol is currently being submitted to the University of Southampton ethics committee for approval of the final survey and information sheet.

Potential participants have already been approached to take part in the Delphi surveys, and further recruitment will take place across July and August. Sixteen health care professionals who expressed interest in the qualitative interviews, but did not take part in an interview due to recruitment capacity being met, have been invited to take part in the Delphi, as they gave consent to be contacted about further research associated with this project. Ten have agreed to be involved and have recommended other health professionals to take part.

As part of the wider STRONG AYA project, a stakeholder forum is set to take place in late September which will gather relevant stakeholder constituencies to raise interest in future involvement with STRONG AYA activities. Recruitment for the Delphi study will be advertised alongside recruitment for the stakeholder forum, via newsletters and social media.

See Table 6 below for a more detailed recruitment plan for the Delphi study.

AYAs & Parents/caregivers/ partners/siblings	Healthcare professionals	Researchers/policymakers
Recruitment target (n=50)	Recruitment target (n=50)	Recruitment target (n=50)
Contact participants who took part in an interview.	Contact participants who took part in an interview.	Contact participants who took part in an interview.
Emailing contacts within the European Cancer community.	Participants who have expressed interest to recommend other professionals to potentially approach for participation.	Contact members of EORTC.
Social media of EU-CAYAS.	Emailing contacts within the European Cancer community.	Contact attendees at the AYA conference.
Youth Cancer Europe charity: contact at charity to email potential participants. Youth Cancer Europe to advertise through social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook).	(Inter)national AYA oncology networks (via ENTYAC, ESMO-SIOPE)) by email/newsletter.	Contact researchers directly from published papers on AYA cancer.

Table 6. Recruitment plan for Delphi

Planned measures to compensate for incurred delays

Delays were incurred to ethics approval and therefore starting qualitative interviews due to aligning the Delphi survey for STRONG AYA with Youth Cancer Europe’s EU CAYAS NET project. Recruitment of AYA participants for the qualitative study was delayed due to conflicting priorities of our collaborators who aided recruitment, however this had no impact in delivering a set of outcomes derived from the interviews to inform the Delphi study.

Creation of the Delphi survey is informed by data from the qualitative interviews and identifying important outcomes from the literature review, which is taking place within Work Package 1 of the STRONG AYA project. There has been delays in the completion of the literature review, which has impacted the development of the Delphi survey. To compensate for any future delays, the distribution of the first survey round has been delayed until September, to allow the literature review to be completed and relevant findings to be added to the final Delphi survey. Postponing until September will ensure the Delphi survey captures all the important outcomes, and allow time for piloting of the survey to take place.

The following measures will be put into place to mitigate potential delays to conducting the Delphi (See Table 7).

Potential delays	Planned measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A planned change in the data holders for the Delphi survey. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amending data sharing agreement, so that University of Southampton will be the data custodian for the Delphi instead of Youth Cancer Europe
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Poor response rates from stakeholders which may result in the survey being open for longer than 3 weeks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regular reminder emails to survey participants to complete Delphi survey
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low recruitment responses, resulting in the target stakeholder numbers not being met. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Calls for recruitment will be sent out in July newsletters, to capture early interest in the Delphi study. Relevant gatekeepers have also been informed of what is needed from them in August, when the final push for recruitment will take place.

Table 7. Planned measures to mitigate potential delays

6 Conclusion

Interviews for the qualitative phase of WP1 are complete (as of 28.06.23). Participants were recruited through a variety of pathways (social media, cancer organisations, support centres, networks, through other participants interviewed). Whilst there was a good response rate from AYAs with/who had a diagnosis of cancer and healthcare professionals; the stakeholder group of parents/caregivers/partners/siblings were most challenging to recruit and the response rate for this group was low despite recruitment efforts engaged with. The Delphi study is due to commence in September 2023. Actions currently being implemented to recruit participants and mitigate potential delays occurring are reminder emails being sent to participants periodically, gaining early interest from potential participants, and informing relevant stakeholder groups of what their involvement requires and timelines for completion of this study. Reflecting on the challenges in the recruitment of potential stakeholder groups, we learned the importance of managing expectations of our collaborators and regular communication through virtual meetings and email to aid building relationships and working together to meet the objectives.

